

<p>FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT STAGES OF MEMOIR GENRE IN THE KARAKALPAK LITERATURE</p>		<p style="text-align: center;">Literature</p> <p>Keywords: memoir, psychology, novel, poetry, genre, composition, disposition, style, workmanship skill, manner, realism, comparativism, impressionism, plot, fact, history, interior.</p>
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<p style="text-align: center;">Abstract</p> <p>The issues such as the role of memoir genre in Karakalpak literature, its functional significance, development stages, development and formation of the genre are illuminated in this article. Especially the conceptions linked with the human phenomena, his/her fate in the crossroads of important two epochs in Karakalpak literature has been explained. The memoir genre has been evaluated as a literary phenomenon. It is enriched by the meditations of the world and Russian theoretic scientists. In particular, he addressed the point of view of scientists such as English textologist Rolland Bart. The works of such authors as Berdaq, Q. Kamalov, J. Aimurzaev, G. Esemuratova, J. Izentaev have served the object of analysis. Also, the article was based on historical-biographical, structural-semantic methods of analysis. The considerable comments about the development of the memoir literature are given.</p>		

As it is known, there are specific developmental laws, evolutionary development, stages, principles of formation of any literary phenomenon. In particular, the base and opportunity were created to appear new genres in the Karakalpak literature, after the second half of the last century. Particularly, it can be said that "the 60th years is the special appearance of development of the Karakalpak literature, and the prose that has declined, has risen to a leading position. It is a fact that the theme and meaning of prosaic works include many branches of the national economy. It also enriches according to the aspect of genre. The Karakalpak prose consisted of essay, sketch, fairytales, artistic publicism, and a number of stories ago, after that genre quantity of prosaic works have also been differed" [9, p.141], - emphasized the critic Nurlan Nasrullayev. Indeed, there are some definitions in this quote. In particular, although the first roots of the memoir genre belonged to those periods, they more developed during the independence years. Let's give attention to the history, we can say that the memoir story titled "The heart of the orphan" of J. Aymurzaev, a prominent figure who is famous for his great prose works, is the first step. This story covers the period from the first part of the writer to the meeting of writers during the Soviet Union's in 1934 year to the meeting with M. Gorky. The first example of memoir in Karakalpak literature is J. Aymurzaev's story "The heart of the orphan" (1967, 1983), it is expressed the adventures of writer in his childhood and youth.

After that, creating memoir works such as K. Sultanov's "Memory story" (Amudarya, 1971, № 5), "Life notebooks" (1971), K. Ayimbetov's "Memories of the past days" (1972), serve to expand ideological, methodological, notional and form aspects of the genre.

The influence of the "Baburname" memoir work of Babur which was created as literary phenomenon in the Turkic literature, is remarkable to the literature of the relative people. It is clear example of our opinion that the work of Berdaq "Umrin" ("My life"), "Umrin" ("My life") of Otesh poet, in Karakalpak literature, are also appreciated as memories of classical word

jewellers. We can see notional features specific to memoir genre in the poem of Berdaq “Umrim” (“Mylife”). For example:

O'n birimda jonim yoqdim,
 O'n uchimda buzoq boqdim,
 Yetimlik azobin totdim,
 Qayg'uli bolalik umrim [3, p. 47].
 (I suffered at eleven years,
 At thirteen I fed the calf,
 I suffer from the orphanhood,
 My sad childhood life)

Another aspect of memoir is that the poet's idea in the text of this poem is remembered to us the great canvas of epic poem. The poet can express a clear picture of the sorrows of his life, his bitter life, and the pain of his heart in his emotionally-expressed senses. The purpose of this is that **each genre has its disposition**. Transforming it into a composition is only an emotional process linked with the poetic skill of the writer.

The hard life of the people during the First World War and after the post-war, the famine, the lack of bread than the hardships of orphanhood are highly described in the memoir essay of J. Aymurzaev “The heart of the orphan”, writers such as G. Gulom, Oybek, A. Qahhor. Memoir essay begins, as follows:

“I was proud, my eyes were goggled and I was black boy. The orphanhood heartbreaking of my heart from childhood accompanies to me. Until the age of seven, I do not know how “the sting was sown” to my heart. It “choked” my freedom, stooped down on my shoulder. The dawn begins with the opening of my eyes, and the sunset blocks my face with tears as downpour. My day is long, and my night is calmness” [1, p.5].

The author gives a brief indication - explanation to the reader at the exposition of the work. This reflects his heavy responsibility as expressing next details to the reader with interesting, adventurous way with hearty heart expression. This essay can serve an important attribute to develop the memoir genre in the Karakalpak literature. In this work, the writer widely uses the chronic type of plot. Namely, in the memoir story, “B event happened after event A” (D. Kuranov).

In the introduction of the memoir story, as the writer said that the pains of my orphanhood encompasses all my life from the age of seven. Then he wrote the sharp truth that he lived with sorrow, grief from the morning to the evening during his life. In general, the poetic skill in the story proves that the writer is a deep erudite man of world literature. The **leitmotif** of the story - anxious fate of the orphan attracts the attention of the reader. Such expressing method is rare literary phenomenon that occurs in world-wide novelists such as Tolstoy, F. Dostoevsky, O. Balzac.

The memoir genre is presumably studied with dividing it into two periods in Karakalpak literature:

1. The memoir works before the independence (1960-1990 years);
2. The memoir works after independence (from 1991 to the present);

This purpose of such classification is that the main purpose which is in the period which each work was created, and its essence is the fate of human. When we research the memoir works which were created in past periods, with the demand of today, studying with comparativism way is justified in particular meaning. Namely, comparison with the comparative way leads to deeply understand the essence of the matter.

Until independence, memoir works in Karakalpak literature did not appear smoothly at all. Another great example of poetic researches which have been carried out in this area, is the memoir work of the great folklore scholar of the Karakalpak people, writer Kally Ayimbetov's "The memories of the past days". As it was said in the introduction of this work: "Kalli Ayimbetov participated in scientific expeditions which were organized in Karakalpakstan by A. Melkov, S. E. Malov, A. Sokolov, S. Tolstov, P. Ivanov in order to gather the Karakalpak people's ethnography and folklore from the thirty years, as the translator and guide and took part in gathering folklore of our people. I'm just saying "The guide", but he was one of the first people to research the Karakalpak folklore" [2, p.5]. (Kallibek Kamalov).

From the smallest traditions of a nation to the interesting adventures, scientific assumptions, understood truths are written in the memoir work titled "The memories of the past days" of the ethnograph, folklorist scientist, and the exciting writer. The well-known literary critic P. Nurjanov writes about it: "The memoir work of K. Ayimbetov's "The memories of the past days" which is well-known for all, consists of 9 chapters, and in its first section valuable information about the lifestyle of the Karakalpak villages, the traditions and values of our people is given. In the second part is spoken about the history of Chimbay which is one of the five castles in our history, about its lifestyle, political events, and great representatives of it" [10, p.72].

In the memoir story of J. Aymurzaev "The heart of an orphan" the decadent phenomenon which was occurred in the XX century in European literature, is used as a leading motive, in the memoir story of K. Ayimbetov "The memories of the past days", the colourful moments, joys and difficulties of childhood are stated in harmony, namely synchronic way. The purpose of giving this is that there are many differences between plot and composition in both works, although they are created in the same time, it has been four years between written time of the two memoirs. In the first memoir work - the degradation which was bored the spirit of person, determines the purpose of the writer as the red thread to the end of the work, in the second memoir work is reflected the contradictions of the environment and human. It is possible to conclude that the second work is a historical-chronic memoir:

"I remembered the unpleasant fates of Chimbay in the past, the melody of polite which is shown the people who struggled together with primitive world, although I have heard about them.

The voice of Kalbala Jirov, who is wearing a yellow turban on his head, plays the kobuz and sings heroic epic poem, his voice swings the whole world, is still heard in my ears. They are shown in my eyes and mind” [2, p.52].

In given fragment, the writer's perceptions about the universe and human, the knowledge of human's social skills, the decline of the period, the appearance of the nation; the wonders of fate are embodied systematically in the harmony of morality with taste. The taste is at the higher level, understanding the world manner of human is more. The previous dogmas are only from ancient. It is worth mentioning one fact about it: “The notion” of realism has been discredited both in front of writers and in front of readers - as a result of the sophisticated literary politics and the sophisticated implementation of the method of socialist realism to the creative work in line with its goals. During the years of openness, from the one hand, the documentary sources which expose the real purpose of the authority of the Soviet, and from the other hand, the announcement of various articles about the great writers and poets of the Soviet period has led to the loss of confidence of the people and readers to the past, in general, to artistic expression” [8, p.12]. This situation did not overlook the Karakalpak literature! The exclusion of literature from the social sorrow has led to decline the pure aesthetic taste. Struggle for a pure aesthetic tone was highly described in K. Ayimbetov's memoir story “The memories of the past days”. At first glance, it is impressed in the imagination of reader that they are not connected to each other. However, if we follow the writer's goal, it will be clear that it belongs to their shape aspect. We have some reason to believe that K. Ayimbetov had taken the pen in order to develop it, do not to overlook the fate of the people who lost their way in life, accomplices who failed in the life, his indebtedness sense in front of the people.

The famous British textologist R. Bart calls the writers “transitive type people” (transformer). They intended themselves the highest goals, such as testimony, explanation and learning. As we have already mentioned above, there is symbolic observation in giving the name to the work of K. Ayimbetov “The memories of the past days” which is the specific form of the sample of the memoir literature. Thus, participation of the author as the witness in the work, and the analysis of the reality, as well as evaluating the reality, can be given opportunity to summarize as follows.

The second phase of development and evolution of Karakalpak memoir literature began officially from 1991. In the interpretation of the fates that had been unseen or mixed up in the same genre, the reality was typified the three parts. The first part is the revival of history, the second part is the influence of the Soviet authority, the third part is that the openness gives opportunity to develop with the clearest step to the pure art. From that years, the social and psychological changes which were taking place in the world context, were showing that they were being eroded the existing regime.

The memoir work of outstanding man, a famous writer, Kamal Kamalov's 1995 “In service of the people” which was published in 1995, includes periods from his childhood and the great-little life-troubles of the author. It should be called this work as the product of structural activity. It

is characterized by the fact that the author can combine gradual processes related to a number of human experiences, such as **childhood-youth-student year-teacher-leadership-directorship-old age** for one purpose. The reality in the work fits perfectly with the method of sociological and biographical analysis. It is possible to observe the social status of the person, his/her choice of profession, his/her self-working, studying the science and his/her aspiration to reveal it. The biographic method requires harmonization of the writer with the work. “He pays particular attention to the personal life of the creator, the living environment, the spiritual-psychological state, personal attitudes, inspirational factors for writing the work, laboratory of the creator, and other historical individual issues” [7, p.166].

K.Kamalov contributed to the expansion of the historical-functional, socio-philosophical aspects of the memoir genre in literature with his work “In service of the people”. K.Kamalov gives great attention to **impressionism** in describing the reality. Namely, he emphasizes to see the world in new form. This image is drawn with hatches. The only one reality serves as the base for the emergence of the second reality:

“Our ancestors did not see comfortable places and conditions like today because they underwent much malice in the past, they more moved. So I got involved in leadership work very early, lived among this people, I was needy of them, I experienced their real situation together with them, I grew up deeply understanding the life quarrels. Only spiritual inheritance given as the will from the father to his children, the property, fortified buildings, flat roads, bridges, as well as houses, mosques, madrassahs, country houses, palaces like today did not bequeathed, because our people moved from one place to another. [6, p.179].

The *mercy, duty, endurance, and high nobility* dignities which embraced the dreams of small child of a great nation are reflected in its essence of this dashed text. He works like chemist, who has discovered a new formula, in the interpretation of the image which his entire life is bound to the griefs of the people. Indeed, according to the nature of the personality, each person aspires towards to the happiness. Finally, how do you think that the human that has been given the perfect sense and emotion by the nature, has suffered so much injustice, loss, and worries? After all, nowadays the biggest problem facing human beings in reality is to preserve their identity, is not it? But even if it is difficult at all, it is important that human beings have a great deal of wisdom to live their lives. The author makes a real difference in this way for this purpose. By doing so, he has achieved his clear objective - to speak freely and impartially.

Another example of the Karakalpak memoir literature during the independent years is the memoir work of G.Esemuratova about “Academician Sabir Kamalov”. This memoir is about the scientist, the husband of woman who has lived together for a lifetime, spent “good and bad” and “bitter and sweet” days together. The main hero of the memoir novel, Sabir Kamalov. She gave the memories which the scientist underwent different difficulties to reach the academic level, and true description of his contemporaries about him. The analysis and perceptions presented in this book, along with the disclosure of the psychological state, also fully reflect the author's view according to our look. The following questions can be found the answers that the development of

Karakalpakstan, appearing the railroads, and what can be done to improve the people's lifestyle. Navruz Japakov told about young and prospective talents “There is a lack of highly educated personnel, especially academic staff, namely, doctors of science and candidates of science. We are going to send you, our self-sacrificing braves, to postgraduate courses to big cities. Well, who takes this task to own responsibility and promises to go to study” said Navruz Japakov and looked at the young man sitting in front of him with insistent look ...” [5, pp.110-111]. After this detail, the next life of the future academician was thoroughly analyzed, and his future, difficulties which he faced in the life, were expressed. Namely, it was narrated about the “sweet” moments connected with the fate of G. Esemuratova, also, about that his family and scientific work were not easy, the author considers her hero not only as his husband, but also as a person who is indifferent to the fate of the scientist.

“There are three types of artistic descriptions in literature: portrait, landscape, interior (the property of the universe). However, it should be noted that the entire appearance of these descriptions serves to do the sole purpose - **to describe a man**” [4, p.118]. It is evident that the inner world of person is being analyzed in the interpretations of G. Esemuratova.

Also, during the independence years the essay “The trials of hearts” of J. Izentaev can be evaluated as the memoir work which was expressed in special compact form, in the Karakalpak memoir prose. Here, the author tried to describe all reality as far as possible by look of painter. However, the laws of the memoir genre incarnates to call the work as “essay” from the point of view of the artistic nature of text, from the point of memorizing, recalling in memory.

Another important aspect is that the works which were created in this genre, can be systematically studied in two ways:

1. Works related to the socio-political reality;
2. Works related to the pure artistic aesthetic reality, the living conditions.

In general, in Karakalpak literature has been conducted extensive researches for the evolutionary development, laws, formation and stabilization of the memoir genre. Nowadays the works which the scientists and writers synthesize the aspects of genre belong to Europe in their artistic researches, their aspects linked with the history of the Turkic people, and have been formed as the epic poems form, improvisation form from ancient, have been undergone major changes and innovations.

Memoir works can be explored in the form of attribution (attribute), namely, reliable illuminating the facts, how the author treats the documentary material, as mutual harmony phenomenon of the literary artifice and vital material. It always does the mission of transmitting (incarnating the reality) different genres in any poetry of genre.

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